

Numerical simulation of magnetic drug delivery to human maxillary sinus

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Abstract

Magnetic drug targeting (MDT) is a drug delivery method based on attraction of ferromagnetic particles to high gradient magnetic source placed in target area. In this study, drug delivery to human maxillary sinus using MDT method was numerically simulated. Realistic 3-D models of nasal airway including nasal cavity and maxillary sinus before and after a virtual endoscopic surgery were used in these simulations. Ferromagnetic micro-particles were injected at the nostril and their trajectories in the presence of an imposed magnetic were analyzed. Micro-particles consisting of ferromagnetic core and drug shell were considered for drug delivery simulations. Static magnetic field generated by permanent magnet was applied as an external excitation for MDT. Effect of magnetic field strength, airflow rate and particle diameter on drug deposition in the maxillary sinus for pre- and post-surgery models were studied. The simulation results proved the effectiveness of MDT method as a new approach for targeted drug delivery to human maxillary sinuses.

Keywords: Human airway, Maxillary sinus, Drug delivery, Magnetic

1. Introduction

Magnetic drug Targeting (MDT) is a method used for drug delivery to specific sites in human body. In this method, particles moving in a fluid flow are steered by a gradient magnetic field to target area. Particles are composed of drug covered ferromagnetic core materials. In the presence of external magnetic field, a magnetic moment is induced in the ferromagnetic materials. Interaction of external magnetic field with the induced magnetic moment exerts a net force on the particle. This force is known as magnetophoresis effect and is the cause of particle attraction toward magnetic source. Magnetophoresis force directs the particle to regions with high magnetic field gradient. Magnetic drug targeting is utilized as an efficient strategy for drug delivery to tumours and infected regions in respiratory tract and blood vessels.

In the recent years, several studies on application of magnetic drug targeting method to respiratory tract were carried out. Dames et al. [1] reported their numerical and experimental studies on drug delivery to lung with the aid of magnetic field. They first performed numerical simulations in a lung bifurcation model. Then, they studied *in vivo* drug delivery to mice lungs. Xie et al. [2] investigated aerosol deposition due to magnetic field in an *in vitro* bifurcation model. They also examined magnetic drug delivery to mouse trachea and deep lung. Xi et al. [3] numerically simulated magnetophoretic guidance of particles in a realistic human nasal model. The object of their study was to investigate drug delivery to the olfactory region. Pourmehran et al. [4] performed numerical simulations on magnetic drug targeting to a realistic model of human tracheobronchial airway.

Detailed CFD studies of the realistic geometry of the human upper airway have attracted the attention of the researchers in past decade [5-11]. Steering particle covered drugs to human maxillary sinus has been quite challenging in respiratory drug delivery. Abouali et al. [12] suggested endoscopic surgery for more efficient drug delivery to human maxillary sinus. They

performed numerical simulations on human realistic nasal model before and after surgery. Bahmanzadeh et al. [13] performed the same procedure for the Sphenoid sinus.

In this study, the use of magnetic drug targeting method for more efficient drug delivery to human maxillary sinus was examined. A realistic model of human upper airway and sinuses were used in the present investigation. Virtual endoscopic surgery was performed on the model. Ferromagnetic micro-sphere drug carriers were injected at the nasal airway inlet and the effect of a non-uniform magnetic field on their transport and deposition was numerically investigated.

2. Theory

When the airflow field is known, motion of micro-particles may be studied through the Lagrangian approach, which uses Newton's second law. Accordingly,

$$m_p \frac{d\mathbf{v}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_D + m_p \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F}_M \quad (1)$$

where m_p is the particle mass, \mathbf{v}_p is the particle velocity, \mathbf{F}_D is the drag force, \mathbf{g} is the acceleration of gravity, and \mathbf{F}_M is the magnetophoretic force. The fluid drag force per unit mass exerted on the particle is expressed as:

$$\frac{\mathbf{F}_D}{m_p} = \frac{f}{\tau_p} (\mathbf{v}_f - \mathbf{v}_p) \quad (2)$$

Here, f is Morsi and Alexander drag factor [14], τ_p is the particle relaxation time and \mathbf{v}_f is the fluid velocity. Particle characteristic time is given by,

$$\tau_p = \frac{\rho_p d_p^2}{18\mu_f} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_p is the particle mass density, d_p is the particle diameter, and μ_f is the fluid viscosity.

The magnetophoretic force exerted on the particle is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_M &= \frac{4}{3} \pi r_p^3 \mu_0 (\mathbf{M} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} \\ &= \frac{4}{3} \pi r_p^3 \mu_0 (\mathbf{M} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{H} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where r_p is the particle radius, μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of free space, \mathbf{M} is the magnetization of particle (due to external magnetic field), and \mathbf{H} is the external magnetic field intensity at the location of particle. Magnetization is a function of magnetic field intensity.

In order to evaluate the magnetic field intensity in a domain, the Maxwell equations given by,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}_F \quad (6)$$

are solved. Here, \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{J}_F are, respectively, the magnetic flux density (induction) and the current density. Additionally, the magnetic induction is given as

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu_0(\mathbf{H} + \mathbf{M}) \quad (7)$$

Equation (6) is needed to close the Maxwell equations:

3. Results

Geometric models of the upper respiratory tract including nasal cavity, sinuses and nasopharynx that were obtained from the CT scan of a male subject are shown in **Figure 1**. Here a virtual Uncinectomy and Middle Meatal Antrostomy (MMA) surgery on the model was performed and the configurations of the airways passages pre- and post-operation are shown, respectively, in **Figures 1(A) and 1(B)**. The surgery was done on left maxillary sinus to improve the inhaled airflow and suspended particles entrance into the maxillary sinus. The steady breathing rates of 5, 10 and 15 Lit/min are used in these simulations. Particles with diameters of 1 and 10 μm are injected at the left nostril and their trajectories are evaluated. The particles are assumed to consist of Fe_3O_4 and drug each with 50% volume fraction. The drug is assumed to have a density of 1000 kg/m^3 . Iron oxide has a density of 5180 kg/m^3 and is a ferromagnetic material. In the presence of a spatially varying magnetic field, the magnetophoretic force acting on the iron oxide fraction of the particle move the particles toward the regions of high magnetic field gradients. The magnetic moments induced in the iron oxide under various magnetic field intensities are extracted from the magnetization curve provided by Xie et al. [2].

It is assumed that permanent magnets with remanent magnetic flux densities of 0.5, 1 and 1.5 T are used for drug targeting. The cylindrical magnet has 2 cm radius and 2 cm height. As shown in **Figure 2**, the permanent magnet is placed near the left maxillary sinus on a mannequin face.

Figure 3 displays magnetic flux density contours for a permanent magnet with remanent magnetic flux density of 1.5 T. Contours are plotted for side view in **Figure 3 (A)** and for the top view in **Figure 3 (B)**. These cross sections both pass through the middle of cylindrical magnet. High gradient and magnitude of magnetic field near the permanent magnet, as seen in the contours, cause the migration of ferromagnetic particles towards the magnetic source.

A series of simulations were performed with the airflow conditions of 5, 10 and 15 L/min. **Figure 4** shows the results of deposition of drugs in the maxillary sinus caused by magnetic field. Deposition fractions in the maxillary sinus are plotted versus the magnetic field strength and are compared for pre- and post-surgery models for different breathing rate and particle sizes. The results indicate that the highest particle capture occurs for the low airflow rates of about 5 Lit/min and particle diameters of the order of 10 μm . Increase of magnetic field strength leads to sharp increase in the deposition fraction for all

cases. Furthermore, in most pre-surgery cases, the deposition fraction is very low even in the presence of magnetic field. The positive effect of magnetic field in deposition of particles in a post-surgery model is also seen in **Figure 5**.

Figure 1. Schematic of computational models of upper respiratory tract (A) Before Surgery (B) After Surgery

Figure 2. Location and direction of permanent magnet. (A) Front view. (B) Side view.

Figure 3. Contours of magnetic flux density (B) in computational domain for a permanent magnet with remanence of 1.5 T. (A) Side view. (B) Top view.

Figure 4. Deposition fraction (DF) in the maxillary sinus for different magnetic remanences (B_r), airflow (Q) and particle diameters (d_p) before and after virtual surgery.

Figure 5. Particle capture in post-operation model, $Q=5$ Lit/min, $d_p=10 \mu\text{m}$. (A) No magnetic field. (B) Magnetic Field with $B_r=1.5$ T.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the effect of magnetic field on particle capture in human upper airway, and in particular in maxillary sinus is investigated. The influences of various physical parameters including breathing rate and particle size on deposition rate were studied. Simulations were performed on nasal passage models before and after endoscopic operation and the results were compared.

It was observed that permanent magnets with high remanent magnetic flux density, markedly increases particle deposition rate in the maxillary sinus regions, in comparison with the absence of magnetic field. This is due to the strong magnetophoretic forces acting on the suspended particles near the magnetic source.

The largest number of particle capture in the maxillary sinus occurred for low breathing rates of about 5 Lit/min for 10 μm particles. This is because of the low inertia and drag forces for these conditions that increase the relative magnitude of the magnetic force and its effectiveness in moving the particles toward the magnetic source.

Comparison of the DF results obtained before and after operation reveals considerable enhancement in particle deposition after the operation for all studied magnetic field strengths, breathing rates and particle diameters. For pre-operation case, only a few 1 μm particles deposit in the maxillary sinus while none of the larger 10 μm particles are deposited.

Earlier Abouali et al. [5] showed that endoscopic surgery increases particle capture in the maxillary sinus. The results presented in this study showed that the presence of magnetic field gradient increases particle deposition in maxillary sinus for both pre- and post-operation situations. The presence of magnetic field, however, increases the particle capture more effectively in post-operation condition. Therefore, it is concluded that the employment of magnetic drug targeting after endoscopic surgery is highly effective for drug delivery to human maxillary sinus.

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